

Emotion Regulation and Drug Abuse among Adolescents: A Theoretical Research

ABSTRACT

Emotions, which can be defined as a brief, involuntary patterned-full system response to internal and external stimuli, are helpful for humans to remain attuned with environment. But they can be harmful when they are not regulated well, and in an adaptive manner. Adolescence is the period when rapid physiological, psychological and social changes make this system of emotional experiences much more complex. Positive emotions (curiosity), as well as negative emotion (anxiety, anger, sadness, shame, boredom), must be regulated with adaptive strategies, like cognitive problem solving, problem oriented acting, exercise, relaxation, meditation, music, social interaction etc. But when drugs are used as to regulate the intensity and magnitude of negative emotions, a maladaptive picture of self-regulation is to be posed in form of physiological, psychological, social, economical disturbances and character deterioration. As children grow to the stage of adolescence, emotion regulation process becomes more complex, as the social context is taken into account. The present paper was intended to analyze the review of literature to understand the emotion focused strategies of regulation triggered by external and internal environment, adopted by drug addicted adolescents and those at risk of to be victim of drug abuse. Systematic analysis of various studies demonstrate that maladaptive emotion regulation strategies or inability to regulate emotions effectively can play an important role as the causing factor, maintenance factor and may have implication in recovery also.

Keywords: Emotion Regulation, drug abuse, adolescence